

IDENTIFYING AND ASSESSING LUNAR ANALOGUES: A CRITERIA-BASED FRAMEWORK FOR MINERAL RESOURCE APPLICATIONS. M. J. Pereira Nunes Segundo¹ and A. Calzada Diaz¹, ¹European Space Resources Innovation Centre/Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology – ESRIC/LIST (mercio-john.pereira-nunes-segundo@list.lu)

Introduction: Lunar mineral exploration faces critical limitations, particularly the lack of in situ data, the strong reliance on remote sensing, and the high degree of geological uncertainty. The definition of terrestrial analogues is challenging as Earth’s plate tectonics and fluid-driven remobilization processes, including weathering-related redistribution under near-surface conditions can significantly change the distribution and concentration of elements within the crust. These factors complicate the identification of terrestrial environments that preserve geological conditions directly comparable to those seen on the Moon.

This study aims to establish a set of criteria to assess the relevance and applicability of lunar analogues already described in the literature and propose new analogue environments, focusing on structural and lithological controls on mineral concentrations (e.g., REEs, Fe, Ti, etc.), where the hydrothermal footprint is minimum and primary magmatic processes dominate or where impact events cause any elements remobilization.

Methodology: The method combines a systematic literature review at first documented terrestrial lunar analogues and earlier detailed lunar geological mapping (e.g., Bossa Nova Target ^[1,2] and Lalande, forthcoming) for REEs exploration as basis of classification system.

The Classification: Here is being proposed a hierarchical framework (Figure 1), moving from basic resource characteristics (element type, mineralogy, grade) to geological and planetary context. This structure ensures that the analogues are evaluated step by step, preventing overinterpretation of similarities. In addition, it communicates, in a straightforward way, confidence about the similarity between the analogue and the reference lunar deposit.

The proposed analogues Level 0 to 2 are thought to offer insights into geochemical behavior and vector for the formation of those deposits in lunar environment. In a first moment, it cannot be used to infer geological context and processes, while the Level 3 – 5 can provide more information in this point of view.

It is important to highlight those Level 2 criteria thresholds, intended to ensure that the selected analogue is not only mineralogically consistent with the lunar target but also shows concentrations sufficiently significant to justify exploration or resource evaluation studies. In this sense, the classification does not rely solely on compositional similarity, but also on economic and volumetric relevance.

Level 4 analogue status, in contrast, is reserved for deposits that could reproduce inferred petrogenetic evolution, and enrichment mechanisms (e.g., mingling and mixing ^[1]) or secondary processes that led to mineral/elemental accumulation in an area.

Following it, the Level 5 status specifies the broader geological context in which the resource occurs, including tectonic setting, sedimentary or volcanic systems, and large-scale geodynamic processes. For Mars, geological processes, such as sedimentation under different depositional systems, volcanism, and fluvial activity, are comparable to those on Earth, which makes analogue five status possible. In contrast, the Moon presents challenges once tectonic activity is minimal or absent, limiting direct comparisons with Earth-style geological systems.

Figure 1. Planetary Analogues Classification system for resources exploration.

Next Steps: The resulting short listed high-fidelity analogue sites will be prioritized for a preliminary field validation, with the goal of calibrating exploration workflows and reducing the operational gap between lunar orbital observations and practical mineral exploration strategies tailored to the Moon.

References: [1] Pereira Nunes II, M. J. (2025). [Unpublished master’s thesis]. European Space Resources Innovation Centre (ESRIC), GeoPlaNet Master Program. [2] Pereira Nunes II, M. J. & Calzada Diaz, A. (2025), ELS 2025.